

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Impact of community health nursing in the health status of the residents of Barangay Calantipay

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Abstract

The undergraduate nursing students of SMCB in their second and third year are trained and motivated to respond with competence and compassion to the health needs of residents in underserved communities. By conducting health education, environmental cleanliness campaign, supervised immunization, deworming, rehabilitation and the like, they can elevate the health status of the communities for the better.

Community Health Nursing provides learning in the form of tasks that involve the assessment of community health needs, identification of health problems, planning of activities and evaluating the effectiveness of the plans formulated in response to the identified problems. They also implement solutions and monitor the progress of their health plans.

Community nursing exposure within the supervision of competent clinical instructors facilitates an increasingly important experience for undergraduate nursing students. Therefore, nursing education providers and health services must ensure that student nurses are exposed to high quality community that provide suitable learning experiences for them to acquire the skills, knowledge and attitudes required for optimum health services in the future

Keywords: Community placement; Mentorship; Nursing assessment; Qualitative evidence synthesis; Community nursing

1. Introduction

Community-based nursing in recent years has received much attention from nursing schools in the Philippines as a suitable solution to existing and future health problems and challenges.

This study was aimed at analyzing the concept of community-based nursing, its impact on people and health care. Community Health Nursing focuses on improving the lives of diverse communities of infants, children, adolescents, and adults through education, prevention, and treatment. It includes health promotion, disease prevention and maintenance of health which is the foundation of community evidence-based care.

The primary goal of Community Health Nursing is to enhance the capacity of individuals, families and communities to cope with their health needs. Its focus is disease prevention, which is categorized into three levels of prevention: primary, secondary, and tertiary. The community health nursing of the students at St. Mary's College of Baliuag, Inc. assigned in Barangay Calantipay, City of Baliuag, Bulacan, Philippines emphasized the importance of the three (3) levels of disease prevention.

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2. Review of Related Literature

According to the 2020 Census, Barangay Calantipay's population was 3,522 represented by 2.09% of the total population of Baliwag City. Its entire household population was 2,784, broken down into 698 households or an average of 3.99 members per household. Specifically, the age group with the highest population in Calantipay is 15 to 19 years old, with 305 individuals while the age group with the lowest population is 80 and over, with 17 individuals. (<https://www.philatlas.com>)

The community health nursing services of the nursing students at Barangay Calantipay were focused on the three levels of prevention namely:

2.1. Primary prevention

To avoid disease or adverse event to occur, the nursing students assigned in the community conduct health education, assist the community health nurse in immunization, cleanliness campaign or initiation of an exercise program with the goal of disease prevention.

2.2. Secondary prevention

In secondary prevention, disease is detected and treated early, often before symptoms are present, thus minimizing serious consequences. The nursing students assist the community health nurse in the screening programs which include measuring vital signs, body mass index calculation, blood glucose, cholesterol measurement and conducting health education and home visits.

2.3. Tertiary prevention

In tertiary prevention, an existing chronic disease is managed to prevent complications or further damage. For diabetic patients the focus is made on screening. Once diagnosed with diabetes, insulin levels are managed, and feet are regularly examined for signs of complication.

A study conducted on the Community Health Nursing competency of Public Health Nurses in Taiwan, revealed that the crucial factors among public health nurses working in the community were age and communication competence. By accumulating practical experiences through the years, public health nurses' communication competence can improve, and enhance the psychological and organizational empowerment in the workplace. (Kuo et al. 2021).

The Community Health Nursing students working with the residents in the community formed partnerships with them as they accomplish health assessments, plan health improvement programs and health promotion plans, as they become the integrator and coordinator in the community healthcare management team in the community. The purpose of Community Health Nursing as a subject in the BSN curriculum is to provide knowledge and practical services based on cultural diversity. Services are provided according to the needs and community conditions of the people by caring for individuals and families with health problems throughout life. Nursing students respond to community-based experiences of people who are facing real-life issues using a problem and service-based approach, providing basic health care in consideration of factors affecting health. (Zeydani et al. 2023)

Building trust and relationships with individuals and local leaders in the community, the nursing students develop a strong understanding of people's backgrounds, experiences, and the social factors that influence health, with the goal of practicing humble service, empathy and compassionate care. One of the primary goals of Community Health Nursing is to raise awareness regarding public health issues and help stop the spread of preventable diseases and illnesses. (Purdue Global, 2022)

The responsibilities of nursing students doing Community Health Nursing are to promote healthy living, disease prevention, and if necessary, supervised medical treatment. Additionally, they create programs that promote health and collect data to identify community needs. (St. Catherine University, 2021)

The crucial role of Community Health Nursing is to provide essential and personalized healthcare services to individuals within the communities. In the field of community research, Community Health Nursing care engages in systematic investigation, collection, and analysis of data for solving problems and enhancing community health practice. (ksu.edu.sa)

Community Health Nursing is valuable because of its primary goal to raise awareness about public health issues and help stop the spread of preventable diseases and illnesses. (<https://www.waldenu.edu/programs>, 2021)

The nursing students involved in community service utilize the principle of Community Organizing Participatory Action Research (COPAR) an important tool for community development as they empower the residents to generate community participation in development of activities. Once empowered, the people can eventually take over the management of development programs in the future. (Nursing Hero, 2024)

Recognizing the vital role of Community Health Nursing in the BSN curriculum, SMCB offers seven units (7) where the students learn to take charge of the welfare and overall health status of the residents. They also focus on improving the lives of diverse communities of infants, children, adolescents, and adults through health education, disease prevention, and treatment. As attested by a community nurse instructor, the nursing students performing community services are instruments in equalizing health care in diverse populations, so that care is more affordable, and well-coordinated.

The nursing students performing Community Health Nursing play a crucial and multifaceted role in conducting health education and promotion, community assessment, disease prevention and surveillance, counseling and support encompassing a broad spectrum of activities aimed at improving overall community well-being (Khairwar, 2024)

This research emphasized how Community Health Nursing efforts significantly improved residents' overall health status, including health education, preventive care, and routine health assessments. It was noted that residents who actively participated in CHN programs reported reduced chronic illness symptoms and increased adherence to preventive practices, such as vaccination and regular screenings. It further showed that personalized approaches enabled nurses to establish trust and rapport, positively influencing residents' willingness to engage in health initiatives. The research concluded that sustained CHN efforts are crucial for long-term health improvement in marginalized communities (Williams et al., 2019).

According to a study by Patel and O'Brien (2020), Community Health Nursing plays a significant role in managing chronic diseases, particularly in low-income neighborhoods. This study found that CHN programs focusing on disease-specific education and lifestyle modifications significantly contribute to controlling hypertension, diabetes, and other prevalent conditions. Community health nurses provide consistent follow-up, medication management, and personalized counseling, resulting in better disease management and health maintenance.

Khan and Rivera (2021) explored how Community Health Nursing supports health promotion and disease prevention in rural communities. They found that Community Health Nursing (CHN) programs that incorporate health promotion activities, such as nutrition counseling, physical activity, and mental health support, substantially and positively impacted overall health status in the community. Residents exposed to CHN educational workshops displayed improved knowledge and attitudes toward preventive healthcare.

A recent study conducted by Flores and Gonzales (2023) evaluated the health impact of CHN programs on underprivileged communities in the Philippines. Their findings revealed that CHN activities, such as immunization drives, maternal and child health services, and sanitation education, significantly improved the health indicators of communities with limited access to formal healthcare. The study documented reductions in infant mortality rates and improvements in maternal health as primary outcomes.

A study done by Emrani et al. (2024) focused on the impact of service-based learning in the health education competencies of students in Community Health Nursing internships found out that some students have poor health education competencies. Therefore, it is recommended by the authors that educational interventions on service-learning can help improve this gap in knowledge and skills of the nursing students. The nursing administrators and instructors should empower the nursing students in service-learning techniques to become more relevant and competent community health workers.

The findings revealed that Community Health Nursing is experienced as a community engagement strategy as well as a beneficial learning strategy. However, some challenges were experienced by nursing students including financial and accessibility constraints and limited involvement of educators. (Nuuyuma, V. et al., 2022)

Objectives of the Study

This qualitative evidence synthesis examined one hundred-twenty (120) undergraduate nursing students experiencing community nursing exposures for AY 2024 - 2025. This study's research questions include the following:

- What is community health care nursing?
- How is community health care nursing conducted in Barangay Calantipay?
- How did the community health care nursing contribute to the residents' health status?

3. Methods

This study employed a qualitative descriptive design that was used to explore the experiences of nursing students during the community health nursing engagements in Barangay Calantipay.

A questionnaire written in vernacular for easy assimilation and understanding was administered to the residents of Calantipay community and the assigned students in Community Health Nursing. The respondents elicited informative data resulting from gained experiences encountered during community immersions done by the students for the benefit of the residents. Focus group discussions with the students were also employed as verifiable data collection.

3.1. Presentation of Data

Table 1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
19 years of age	22	22.00
20 years of age	29	29.00
21 years of age	27	27.00
22 years of age	10	10.00
23 years of age	4	4.00
25 years of age	1	1.00
26 years of age	1	1.00
28 years of age	2	2.00
35 years of age	1	1.00
43 years of age	1	1.00
41 years of age	1	1.00
Sex		
Male	28	28.00
Female	71	71.00

As shown in the table, 22 (22%) of the respondents are 19 years old, 29 (29%) are 20 years old, 27 (27%) are 21 years old, ten (10) or 10% are 22 years old, four (4) or 4% are 23 years old, and two (2) or 2% are 28 years old. On the other hand, the ages 25, 26, 35, 43 and 41 have one (1) respondent each.

Table 2 shows that 96 or 96% of the respondents are single and 3 or 3% are married. In terms of educational attainment, 3 (3%) of the respondents have attained elementary education, 7 (7%) have finished high school whereas most of them are still in college with 89 (89%).

Table 2 Social Status and Educational Attainment of the Respondents

	Indicators	Frequency	Percentage
Social Status	Single	96	96.00
	Married	3	3.00
Educational Attainment	Elementary	3	3.00
	High School	7	7.00
	College	89	89.00

Table 3 Health Survey Tool Administered to Respondents

I. Primary health prevention							
A. Health program	5	4	3	2	1	T	Mean
Drink 8 glasses of water everyday	85	10	4	0	0	99	4.82
Sleep at least 8 hours a day	83	12	0	3	1	99	4.75
Eat vegetables to help in regular digestion	85	11	2	1	0	99	4.82
Avoid eating fatty food	80	13	5	0	1	99	4.73
Refrain from eating salty food	79	15	4	1	0	99	4.74
Wash very well the vegetables before cooking	87	9	3	0	0	99	4.85
Eat fresh fish instead of canned goods and pork	76	15	5	1	2	99	4.64
Avoid frequent eating of fried and oily food	82	12	4	1	0	99	4.77
Minimize eating fast food like Jollibee, MacDonald, etc.	80	14	3	2	0	99	4.74
Refrain from using food condiments like monosodium glutamate (MSG), mix fried seasonings	80	15	4	0	0	99	4.77
Cleanliness program	5	4	3	2	1	T	Mean
Take a bath regularly everyday	93	6	0	0	0	99	4.94
Wear clean clothes everyday	94	5	0	0	0	99	4.95
Use the toilet properly	95	4	0	0	0	99	4.96
Do not throw garbage anywhere	89	7	2	0	1	99	4.85
Clean your house regularly	86	12	1	0	0	99	4.86
Regular washing of dirty clothes	87	11	1	0	0	99	4.87
Provide garbage cans at home	89	9	1	0	0	99	4.89
Provide toilet at home for family use	91	7	1	0	0	99	4.91
Regular washing of dirty plates after using	92	7	0	0	0	99	4.93
Wash hands before and after eating	90	7	1	0	0	99	4.90
Regular exercises program	5	4	3	2	1	T	Mean
Exercise regularly to prevent getting fat	79	16	3	1	0	99	4.75
Exercise daily to prevent high blood pressure	84	12	2	1	0	99	4.81
Exercise to improve memory	77	20	2	0	0	99	4.76

Exercise to promote regular sleep	81	14	4	0	0	99	4.78
Exercise to minimize life's stress and tension	85	12	2	0	0	99	4.84
Exercise to strengthen the bones	82	15	1	1	0	99	4.80
Exercise to improve body condition	86	12	1	0	0	99	4.86
Exercise to prevent increasing the blood sugar	84	11	4	0	0	99	4.81
Exercise to facilitate the digestion of food	87	11	1	0	0	99	4.87
Exercise to promote regular body waste disposal	92	5	2	0	0	99	4.91
II secondary prevention							
A. Health center program	5	4	3	2	1	T	Mean
Monitor the blood pressure of the residents	91	8	0	0	0	99	4.82
Check the body temperature of the residents in the community	85	13	1	0	0	99	4.85
Monitor the body weight of the residents (children, adults and elderly)	91	8	0	0	0	99	4.92
Assist the public health nurse in the vaccination of children	92	7	0	0	0	99	4.93
Help in monitoring the blood glucose of the residents with diabetes	90	9	0	0	0	99	4.91
Examine the skin conditions of the diabetic residents in terms of the presence of skin infection and wounds and report immediately to the barangay nurse for follow-up treatment	89	9	1	0	0	99	4.89
Help in the feeding of the malnourished children in the community	93	6	0	0	0	99	4.94
Educate the mothers on what kind of food to be given to their malnourished children	94	5	0	0	0	99	4.95
Teach the mothers on the proper methods of breast feeding their babies	93	6	0	0	0	99	4.94
Educate the mothers on first aid tips when their children have fever, colds and coughs.	91	7	0	1	0	99	4.90
III. Tertiary prevention							
A. Health center program	5	4	3	2	1	T	Mean
Examine and record the sick residents in Barangay Health Center	88	10	1	0	0	99	4.88
Report to public health nurse the sick residents so that proper treatment can be given to them	88	10	1	0	0	99	4.88
Assist in giving the medicines and distribute the prescriptions ordered by the physician to the diabetic residents	88	9	1	0	1	99	4.85
Help in the distribution of prescribed medicines to the residents with high blood pressure	88	9	1	0	1	99	4.85
Report immediately to the community health nurse and doctor the new cases of sickness found in the community	90	9	0	0	0	99	4.91
Assist in giving the medicines against parasites to the children	92	7	0	0	0	99	4.93
Campaign and conduct health teachings against dengue in the community	91	8	0	0	0	99	4.92
Organize the male residents to conduct environmental cleanliness campaign	88	10	1	0	0	99	4.88
Encourage the residents to grow backyard gardening of vegetables for family consumption	90	9	0	0	0	99	4.91
Indicate a designated place where to throw the garbage in the community	90	9	0	0	0	99	4.91

Overall Average	4.86
Very big Help	

Legend: 5- Very Big Help 4- Big Help 3- Enough Help 2- Little Help 1- No help

Table 3 clearly indicates that with the targeted primary health prevention program, the highest mean is 4.85 on the item referring to “wash very well the vegetables before cooking” whereas on cleanliness program the highest mean is 4.96 “using the toilet properly” and on the value of regular exercise program, the highest mean is 4.91 that “exercise can promote regular waste disposal”. As reported by World Health Organization in 2023 that factors like health education, by maintaining personal and environmental cleanliness, the importance of regular exercises for body’s well-being plays a critical role in shaping health and well-being which may include social protection, food systems, education, and environmental factors, among others.

On the other hand, in Secondary Prevention the item that got the highest mean is 4.95 “Educate the mothers on what kind of food to be given to their malnourished children” and in the Tertiary prevention “Assists in giving the medicines against parasites to the children” got the highest mean of 4.93. It is important that during the health education campaign of the nursing students with the mothers they should emphasize the results of the surveys on the importance of washing very well the vegetables before cooking, proper use of toilet and maintain regular exercise as well as the importance of a healthy diet as essential to good health and nutrition. The practices mentioned protect the residents of Barangay Calantipay against many chronic communicable as well as noncommunicable diseases, such as heart disease, diabetes and cancer.

4. Findings of the Study

- The community provides valuable learning experiences of nursing from an alternative perspective of enhancing professional development and understanding of the nurse patient relationship.
- Mentorship of the clinical instructors and inclusion in teams are key factors that influence students' experiences, and this working environment is useful for teaching about holistic care that is person and family centered. Role modeling is enhanced by the pace and proximity of the mentoring relationship.
- The findings of this study demonstrate that exposing students to community engagement can help to intentionally integrate theory and practice, and practice and theory.
- Bringing community-based experiences into the classroom and going out into the community can help students to develop human skills, promote team-based learning and contribute to community engagement. The latter is a skill that can be useful in the students' careers considering the need to empower communities in healthcare.

Recommendations

- Clinical instructors must expose and immerse the nursing students to communities that will provide varied experiential knowledge on health education.
- The administration and teaching staff may provide academic, moral and psychological support to the students for improved performance outcomes.
- The most immediate benefit of community nursing care is the comfort and convenience it offers because the residents receive professional care in a familiar environment of their own homes.
- Nursing students must be further exposed to community nursing care; thus, provide a healthier environment.
- Nursing students must be trained to provide specialized, one-on-one care through a formulation of a treatment plan that is highly designed to the needs and lifestyle of the community residents.
- Student nurses in their community health care exposure, may collaborate with family members, caregivers and support workers for an informed approach to health management.

5. Conclusion

The inherent values of Community Health Nursing experience while undergoing basic training in nursing care is valuable to prepare more complicated cases to handle in the future as registered nurses. The result of this study can be an eye opener for school administration and teaching staff to provide wholistic training to student nurses in critical, problem-solving and humanitarian skills. As future community health nurses they can assume varied roles as an educator, advocate of patient’s care, manager, collaborator, leader and researcher in the community identifying health issues, providing services, and improving community health status resulting from valid research data.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of ethical approval

Ethical clearance to conduct the study was granted by the school Research Ethics Committee.

Statement of informed consent

Permission to conduct the study was secured from the School President, Dean of College, and from the participants of the study.

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